

DEVELOPMENT OF A NEW DESIGN APPROACH FOR EXPERIENCE

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, industry and research communities' interest in Experience Design is growing. However, most of the existing approaches found in literature are defined in an abstract level and they are not easy to implement. In order to fill this gap, the authors of this article studied the way three teams of master students handled the design of an experience for the first time. From the analysis of the three projects, authors identified an underlying design process to Design for Experience. This approach has its roots on current Experience Design models and it incorporates tools from the fields of people-centred design, inclusive design and perceptual evaluation into the process. This article shows the analysis of the aforementioned projects. The results of the analysis will be the starting point of an iterative refinement process that expects to end up becoming a straightforward design process relatively simple to be used by industry.

Keywords: experience, user experience, experience design, design methodology.

INTRODUCTION

Experience Design and User Experience have gained a prominent place on the efforts of both academic research and professional practice communities, especially in the field of interactive products. However, the concept of experience is equally paramount for all the other design fields. From the industrial design point of view, the focus is shifting from the product towards the user and the interaction between the latter and the designed product. Nowadays, literature review reveals that there are many approaches towards experience design, or, as Forlizzi (1997)

names it, "designing for experience". The reviewed literature (Forlizzi, 1997; Battarbee & Koskinnen, 2005; Hassenzahl & Tractinsky, 2006; Ortiz Nicolas & Aurissichio, 2011) showed attempts to define Experience, User Experience and map the ongoing research in the field. Other authors tried to generate unified definitions of the aforementioned concepts (Hassenzahl et al., 2006; Law et al., 2009). At the same time, other authors created frameworks in order to have a basis for designing (Forlizzi & Ford, 2000; Hassenzahl, 2003; Forlizzi & Battarbee, 2004; Knight & Jefsioutine, 2004; Vyas & Veer, 2006; Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). Other research work focused on describing and generating processes or models for what they called "Experience Design" (Shedroff, 2001; Oppelaar et al., 2008; Hassenzahl, 2010), while other approaches named their approaches "Experience-centred Design" (Wright & McCarthy, 2010) or "Experience-driven Design" (Desmet & Schifferstein, 2011). Each of them shows a different way to handle the complexity of the concept "experience", but in general, most of the models attempting to design for experience are developed in a conceptual level (i. e. Shedroff, 2001; Hassenzahl, 2010). Most widely accepted models of design for experience do not describe specific steps or tools that answer the question of how designers can design for experience. This models trait is not random, since they aim at inspiring designers rather than guiding them. Thus, the aforementioned models and frameworks provide abstract valuable knowledge, not step-by-step processes to be followed.

Within this research context, this article shows the first steps of an attempt to develop a more detailed approach towards designing for experience. This approach is being built through the observation of

design projects carried out by students of a specific master's program.

This article is divided in six main chapters. The first chapter points out the specific goals of the study. After that, the second chapter describes the context of the study, including the theoretical basis that the designers have been trained on. The third and fourth chapters show the development of the projects. In the fourth chapter results are discussed and compared with Desmet and Schifferstein's approach (2011), which got published while the study was being carried out. Finally, the section "next steps" shows the proposed starting point for the second iteration of design projects. This second round will be carried out in 2012.

GOALS OF THE STUDY

The goals of the research were the following:

- Compare the design processes followed by the different project teams and find a general process.
- Find gaps and problematic areas along the process, in order to set the starting point to define an experiential design process.
- Evaluate the level of accomplishment of the initial goal, both from designer's perspective and company's and university's perspective.

CONTEXT OF THE STUDY

The three projects were carried during the academic year 2010-2011, by students of a university master program called "Strategic Product and Service Design". The overall goal of the master's program is generate professional designers that are able to promote and generate innovation in products, services and technological processes through strategic design, based on sustainability and people-centred design. The content of the courses examines different fields, along three semesters: the first semester addresses Sustainability and Product Service System design; the second semester focuses on Experience Design and People-Centered Design and the third on Strategic Design. During the fourth semester the students work on their master theses, which are carried out in collaboration with external industrial companies.

PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The current project was held in the second semester of the master, where the students worked on the following courses: Experience Design, People-Centered Design, Interaction and Perception, Interaction Design, Design for All and Advanced Methods for Engineering Design. Except for the last of them, Advanced Methods for Engineering Design, the rest of the courses were meant to be developed along with the project, so that the different content and tools learnt on the courses could be implemented to the project. The subsection "Content of related courses" shows a more detailed description of content of each of the courses.

CONTENT OF RELATED COURSES

The content of the courses included many topics and points of view. The following section shows the main standpoints of them and their expected role in the projects.

Experience Design

The course "Experience Design" focused on the role of Experience towards Design. The theoretical foundations learnt through this course included different viewpoints and definitions of Experience and Experience Design or Design for Experience from different authors (Shedroff, 2001; Hassenzahl, 2010). From them, the course focused both on the descriptive approach of Shedroff (2001), which describes dimensions and phases of an experience, and the approach of Hassenzahl (2010), which stresses the "Why, What and How" levels of the Experience. During the course, the students also reflected on topics such as the role of emotions (Desmet, 2002; Norman, 2004) and sensorial perception on the overall evaluation of a design. Besides this, the course also brought the Experience Marketing viewpoint to debate, as well as the Product Experience Framework (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007).

Finally, the students learnt about how companies such as Philips Design understand experience and make use of tools like Context Mapping (Sleeswijk Visser et al., 2005). The overall goal of the course was to let the student understand the complexity and richness of the topic and help them build their own personal vision on the subject. At the same time, it was expected that

they would take this theoretical framework and integrate it in their own design process, and, thus, make use of it in the project.

Interaction and perception

On the same track, the course “Interaction and Perception” aimed at providing theoretical insights towards the fields of Interaction and Perception. The course defined the basics of interaction design (Moggridge, 2007), interaction, interface analysis, cognitive and physical ergonomics and usability. On the other hand, perception-wise, the course worked on the topics of cognition, emotional response generation process, the sensorial system, semiotics and the concept of affordance. Finally, the course also related to perception evaluation tools from fields like Kansei Engineering or emotion evaluation tools like PrEmo (Desmet, 2003).

People Centered Design

The course called “People Centered Design” was practice-oriented. During the course, the students studied and used different design research tools such as ethnography, co-creative sessions and cultural probes. The use and creation of these tools provided several key insights for their projects.

Interaction Design

The course “Interaction design” also followed a practical approach, where the students learnt the basic about fields like Information Architecture and User Experience Design, using tools like wireframing, paper prototyping and more advanced tools like Arduino boards to learn the basics of interactive prototyping.

Design for All

Finally, the course “Design for All” introduced the students to the field of Universal Design and the ethical considerations that are attached to it. Through this course, the students not only gained insights about the diversity of possible users of their designs but also understood how designing for a bigger amount of different people can lead to create better designs for all the users. Additionally, sensitising tools were introduced to the students.

PROJECT DEFINITION

The students were divided in three design teams of five people each. The academic background of most of them was a bachelor program in Industrial Design Engineering from Mondragon University. It is important to note that, being it was the first time that the master’s program was launched, the students’ age range and professional profiles were diverse. Some of them have worked in industry for several years and they have continued developing part-time jobs while studying the master. One of the authors of this article joined one of the teams as part of his PhD studies, in order to experience and carry out the project personally.

Each semester the students work on a project for a company, and in this case it was developed for Fagor Hometek S. Coop. This company is the Research and Development division of Fagor Electrodomésticos S. Coop., a domestic appliance manufacturing cooperative company in Gipuzkoa (Spain).

The project lasted twelve weeks, and although each of the three projects had a different, distinctive starting point, they shared the same main academic goal: Design an experience answering to the design assignment proposed by the company.

For the first project, the company set a clear target experience: create an experience where parents and their kids would cook together. The second project aimed at redesigning an interactive diet assistant for diabetics and the third one at redesigning a tele-monitoring system for patients after having suffered a heart-stroke. The company’s initial goal for the last two projects was to improve their existing platforms from a user experience perspective.

The expected final results of the project were left deliberately open, due to the novelty of the topic. However, integration of different working methods and tools learnt along the courses of “Experience Design”, “People-Centered Design”, “Design for All” and “Interaction Design” along the process was expected, as well as a testable prototype and a perceptual evaluation of the final outcome, using tools from the course “Interaction and Perception”.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE STUDY

In general, the three projects followed different paths due to the specific design assignments they had. However, five phases can be identified along the process: analysis, formulation, conceptualisation, development and evaluation. These phases did not arise from academic milestones but from the students' natural working process. The following section describes the development of the projects along the phases.

ANALYSIS

All three groups started their projects analysing the design assignment, in order to understand and assimilate the academic goal of the project, as well as the company's interests. In this first step, the design teams set their preliminary design goals and directed their efforts towards learning more on the current experiences or similar ones.

The first project headed towards developing a means to create the experience that was proposed from the beginning, focusing their analysis on building knowledge on the design scenario. The second project defined their goal as to increase desirability of the existing interface by improving the current quality of interaction. The third project also defined their initial goal as to improve the current user experience, but they didn't specify if it was interface-related or not.

Apart from establishing the initial goals, all three groups analysed the current experience in two main ways: ethnography, observation and co-creative sessions on one hand and more traditional information gathering tools on the other.

FORMULATION

The analysis phase helped understand and develop the given design assignment and generate a particular vision on it. According to some authors (Hekkert & van Dijk, 2011), this is one of the most critical parts of the design process. All three design projects ended up the analysis phase further formulating their design goals.

The first project confirmed the initial design goal, specified the ideal age range of the kids and the experiential dimensions of the target experience, following Shedroff's (2001) dimensions of the

experience (figure 1). Thinking about the mentioned six dimensions (significance, breadth, intensity, duration, triggers and interaction) helped the design team build their own design scenario and define the target context and target experience.

Figure 1. Diagram of the six dimensions of the experience according to Shedroff (2001).

Initially, the second team had set their goal at boosting desirability of the interface by improving interaction. In order to do so, they analysed similar web services in the market and then focused on user analysis in two ways: eating related to health issues and lifestyle. Based on that research, they determined different user profiles and decided to broaden the initial user profile from diabetes patients towards a more general public. Moreover, they redefined their design goal towards the generation of a "self-motivated community" that would take care of their alimentation using the redesigned interface.

Figure 2. Healthcare stages and its transitional points of care (above, Philips Design, 2008) and the context description timeline based on the healthcare stages (below).

The third team, whose initial design goal was to improve a tele-monitoring experience, also changed their initial design goal based on the insights found on interviews with real patients. The interviews revealed that this kind of patients had bigger issues through their recovery process to be solved than the discomfort of going to the hospital a couple of times a week. For that reason, the design team depicted four phases of healthcare process (Philips Design, 2008) in a timeline and built a description of the patient's context over it (figure 2). Based on that timeline, the design team re-formulated the main problem to be addressed: the difficulties of the patients to keep the motivation to maintain healthy habits. Therefore, the redefinition of the design goal led to a completely new target experience to be designed.

In this step of the project, the three teams showed their conclusions from the analysis and their vision statements to the company in order to check their opinion and get feedback.

CONCEPTUALISATION

Once target experiences were formulated, the design teams started the conceptualisation phase. Compared with the others, the first team worked relatively longer in this phase because they fixed their vision faster. The second team spent most of its time in the analysis and then the development of the redesigned interface, while the third team took more time redefining the design goal than the others.

The first and the second projects developed their experience proposals according to the initial vision. However, the third team changed completely the initial view and therefore their experience definition was radically different. Their final concept was a social network composed of similarly diagnosed patients. The patients would take part on a game-like activity program while the community helps them go through

their recovery process. The touchpoints would collect medical information that is used to evaluate both the physical conditions and emotional state of the users, so that they progress towards a healthy life and a confident state of mind towards their illnesses.

Due to time constraints, once the Product Service System was defined, the three design teams determined which of the touchpoints could be further designed. The first and the third design teams divided the work in two: the design of the software, including its architecture and interaction, and conceptualisation of the physical components. The second group focused specifically only in the design of the software application, deepening more in terms of the aforementioned architecture and interaction.

After generating different concepts both for the interface and for the touchpoints, the results were shown to the company to decide on which direction to work on. The interface was defined up to a wireframe level in two of the projects (first and third), while the second also had aesthetical proposals to choose from. The conceptualisation of the touchpoints proposed different alternatives to complement the main software application.

DEVELOPMENT

The next step on the development of the projects was to continue developing the interface, already in a prototype level. These prototypes aimed at being tested later on. On the other hand, the first and the third projects developed a small interactive working prototype of the software application, as well as mock-ups of some of the touchpoints.

EVALUATION

Regarding evaluation, the three projects tested their prototypes with users. However, the three testing processes were performed differently. The first team used real users (parents and their kids) to evaluate the software application and perform the experience of "cooking together". While the design team observed their behaviour, they used one of the designed touchpoints and a tablet device with the software prototype.

The second team, which focused on the interaction design, worked out a detailed paper prototype that would serve to test both the usability and the content of the software. The design team evaluated the results co-creatively, asking real users to go through the different screens and make comments on them.

The third team developed prototypes that were tested in a usability and user experience level rather than in a more general experiential one. They used a tablet device with their initial working prototype and used the mock-ups to get extra feedback on the aesthetical appealingness of them as well.

RESULTS OF THE STUDY

The study of the three projects pointed out a basic underlying process. The diagram in figure 3 shows the aforementioned five phases and the main stages included in each of them. This chapter describes the steps of the process further, including the steps of the experimental model and specific tools that have been used along them. Further analysis of the results is shown as well.

ANALYSIS

This phase starts with an assimilation and understanding stage of the academic and company requirements. The three projects had the same academic requirement: "design an experience". However, each of the projects took very different directions from the beginning, in order to fit company's requirements. The main outcomes of this stage were the preliminary goals.

After setting their goals, they analysed the current experience, deepening into four main areas: user, context, product and interaction. They used different tools to gather information about the four areas, making use of their prior knowledge and the tools they have learnt along the course People Centered Design.

Observational research and personal interviews revealed meaningful insights to understand the users and their concerns. Other tools like context mapping (Sleeswijk Visser et al., 2005) helped envision the context and gather theoretical knowledge. The combination of different tools led to a better

understanding of the context and experiential needs of the user.

Figure 3. Diagram of the underlying design process identified throughout the study.

FORMULATION

The most important goal of the analysis phase is to create an informed understanding of which is the vision of the design team towards the initial assignment. Once enough knowledge is gained in the topic, design teams formulated their vision in different levels. The first design team specified their design goal further, defining context parameters, such as users' age ranges, and the dimensions (Shedroff, 2001) of the target experience. Differently, the other design teams redefined their experiential goals first and then formulated the context and target experience.

CONCEPTUALISATION

Conceptualisation phase took several definition steps and different directions. First of all, the three design teams conceptualised the experience according to

their vision. None of the three teams centralised a product as the “generator” of the experience. The three projects first defined the target experience as a Product Service System, and then generated ideas to create different products that would fit there. The final experience was understood more like a set of activities rather than the objects and services that enable them. In this point, the design teams used service design tools they acquired along the first semester of the master. Tools like system maps and blueprints helped them identify different agents, products, activities and existing relationships among them.

DEVELOPMENT

After conceptualizing the Product Service System and its main elements, the design teams chose to develop some aspects of the experience further. In general the projects worked two main fields: a physical touchpoint and interaction design of the main interactive element.

EVALUATION

The initial idea of the university was to evaluate the perception of the resulting designs with tools learnt in the course “Interaction and Perception”, such as Emotional Maps or PrEmo (Desmet, 2003). However, the complexity of the concepts made emotion related tools inappropriate and difficult to implement. For example, the experience of the third team took into account four phases of the patient’s recovery process, and therefore they built an experience that evolves over time. Emotional maps, perception evaluation tools or PrEmo tools are appropriate to measure emotions and perception caused by first impressions in product use, but they are not able to measure the overall quality of experiences over long periods of time. Authors like Karapanos et al. (2008) have measured user experience quality over time, but their measuring techniques involved functional products rather than Product Service Systems. Besides that, time constraints only allowed the development of early prototypes. For that reason, the design teams performed mostly usability tests. Thus, the students missed a general evaluation tool for the overall experience. However, in general, the designer teams and the evaluation boards had positive general impression of the results.

Figure 4. Diagram of the proposed design process compared to Desmet and Schifferstein's (2011) approach.

CONCLUSIONS

After carrying out the three projects, authors consider that they have identified an underlying process among the projects. Generally speaking, the process allows designing with experience in mind, and defines the experience as a system of interrelated touchpoints. The main goal is to fulfil eudemonic needs (Desmet, 2011) such as relatedness, motivation and self-actualisation. The whole process focuses in the “Why” level of Experience (Hassenzahl, 2010), and later models the “What” and “How” levels accordingly. However, the process shows some gaps and, in general, the three projects had implementation difficulties. First of all, the main design goal, defined as “Design an experience”, was not very clear. The company defined three design assignments that did not share a common understanding of what an experience is. Consequently, each of the projects started from a different standpoint and developed in completely different directions. While project one had a target experience from the beginning, the second and third projects were aiming at a redesign of existing product’s experience. This fact makes it more

difficult to assess the projects and make comparisons between them.

Regarding each of the identified phases, the process needs refinement. In the analysis phase, People Centered Design tools are useful for building an experience-centered vision. However, in general, building their own vision and formulating experiential goals and target experience are the most critical parts of the process. In that sense, Desmet and Schifferstein's (2011) Experience-driven Design approach (authors of this study had access to this approach after the study was performed) can be complementary to the current process. The figure 4 shows that Analysis phase of our approach is comparable to the Understand phase of the Experience-driven Design. In the same manner, formulating experience goals, target context, target experience and conceptualizing the Product-Service System are parallel to Envisioning, while concept detailing and development of the touchpoints and prototypes can be grouped in the Create phase. Evaluation phase has been added as a separate

phase. Although Desmet and Schifferstein (2011) consider it part of the Create phase, authors consider it is important enough to be added apart.

Authors consider Experience-driven Design and the current approach share the design spirit, but at implementation level, differences are significant. Experience-driven design is product related, and resulting concepts are much more concrete than the results obtained on this study.

Regarding evaluation, the prototypes built upon this study were not sufficient to test the whole experience concept but focused on a specific touchpoint and its interface. Authors consider it is necessary to find appropriate tools to evaluate the resulting overall experiences.

Finally, commercial applicability of designed experiences is discussed. Currently in our region, most of the industrial companies' strategies are product-centred. Material value is central to their

Figure 5. Definition of the design approach and relationship of course contents. Upper right part relates each of the courses with the four phases (Understand, envision, create and evaluate) of the defined process.

business, and the experiences resulting from the proposed design process do not necessarily fit well in that context. How to make experience design better fit industry needs or how to adapt industry to hedonic and eudemonic needs are interesting challenges.

NEXT STEPS

This study has been a positive first step towards creating our approach toward Designing for Experience. From its development, authors have identified a design process that can be enriched by other institutions' approaches such as Experience-driven Design (Desmet & Schifferstein, 2011). Currently (February 2012), the university is redefining the content and the projects that will be carried out based on the results of this study.

In our approach, Experience is understood as a system of coordinated touchpoints. The goal of the system is to evoke a particular experience. To make this happen, the design team has to create the elements -touchpoints- that will allow the user go through that experience. Currently there is an internal discussion among the research team whether the project should focus on experiences evoked by products or keep it open to a Product Service System basis.

In any case, the courses of the master will provide specific tools for each of the four phases: Understand, envision, create and evaluate. Figure 5 shows in which part of the process each of the courses will be more relevant. "Experience Design" course will be responsible of making the experience be central to the project and it will guide the process throughout the four phases. "People Centered Design" course will provide ethnographic tools to identify needs of users, being especially applicable in the "Understand" phase, and also will introduce the students to co-creation, which can be applied throughout the whole process but specifically along "Understand" and "Create" phases. The course "Interaction Design" will focus on shaping the interaction of different touchpoints, most importantly in the envision, create and evaluation phases, while "Interaction and Perception" will set theoretical basis to understand and envision phases, as well as providing tools to evaluate them. Finally, "Design for All" will work at sensitisation towards

collectives with disabilities, help on the analysis of capabilities and work on inclusiveness.

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